

D2.6 EOOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable reports on the results of the activities as of M41, November 2022 based on the plans originally outlined in D2.2 “Dissemination, communication and stakeholders’ engagement and strategy plan” which was updated in D2.5 EOOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report.

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LINKS

[D2.2] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3786371>

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
AG	Advisory Group (of the EOSC Association)
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
EOSC-Pillar	Coordination and Harmonisation of National and Thematic Initiatives to Support EOSC project
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IPR	Intellectual property rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS	Member State
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Office
TF	Task Force
TI	Thematic Initiatives
TM	Technical Manager
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

The Coordination and Harmonisation of National and Thematic Initiatives to Support EOSC project (EOSC-Pillar), aims to coordinate national Open Science efforts across Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy, and ensure their contribution and readiness for the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). To achieve this, a well-executed communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement plan is necessary.

This deliverable is an update to D2.2 EOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan [D2.2] and D2.5 EOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report [D2.5]. Since the methodology, objectives, stakeholders, campaigns, activities and KPIs largely remain the same, only the updates and changes are noted in this deliverable. Where action items appear in D2.2 but are not mentioned in the succeeding deliverables it means these activities remain unchanged from the original plan.

This document describes the communication and dissemination objectives (Section 1), which include active support for the key activities of the project. This involves the national initiatives survey, harmonisation of procedures for delivering horizontal enabling services for research data, coordination with other initiatives, promotion of FAIR data principles uptake at the national levels, enabling non-commercial transnational services in the EOSC portal, building of an active stakeholder community across the countries covered and proposing business models that ensure the sustainability of EOSC-Pillar's services. This was carried out through planned activities, organised through campaigns (Section 2.1) and horizontal communication activities (Section 2.3). Campaigns that were carried out are:

- Campaign 1: Showcasing Diverse Use Cases & Community-Driven Pilots
- Campaign 2: Policy and Legal Framework Recommendations
- Campaign 3: Communicating the National Initiatives Survey and Outcomes
- Campaign 4: Support for Onboarding New Services
- Campaign 5: Promoting the Open Call for Services
- Campaign 6: Communications Support for Stakeholder Engagement Activities
- Campaign 7: Promoting Training and FAIR Data Services

EOSC-Pillar has also spearheaded several joint activities with the INFRAEOSC-05 projects through the Cross-Project Collaboration Board Task Forces.

1 Introduction

EOSC-Pillar supports the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, and Italy, leveraging national initiatives of the Member States (MS) and Thematic Initiatives developed by research communities working in national and European collaborations to build a future based on Open Science and FAIR data practices.

The activities reported in this deliverable are based on the objectives, value propositions and methodology outlined in D2.5 “EOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report” [D2.5], offering an overview of the project’s outreach and impact right before the end of the EOSC-Pillar project (finishing in December 2022), following its extension.

Like many other Horizon 2020 projects, EOSC-Pillar’s communication activities were also impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak from 2020 up until early 2022, particularly in terms of events.

An overview of the EOSC-Pillar’s second year of activity can be found in the Second Annual Report, published on Zenodo¹.

1.1 Overview of Main Activities

To attain its long-term objectives, the EOSC-Pillar Work Packages are carrying out a range of different activities, also described in D2.2:

- **Analyse** the state of the art of national initiatives and compute and data services, and support consolidation
- **Harmonise** procedures for the delivery of horizontal enabling services for research data across countries
- **Coordinate** with other initiatives to achieve harmonisation for an inclusive EOSC
- **Promote** FAIR data uptake at national levels and across scientific communities and borders
- **Enable** non-commercial transnational services to be accessible through the EOSC portal
- **Build** an active stakeholder community of EOSC supporters in each country
- **Propose** viable business models for the sustainable provision of transnational services

The main focus of Work Package 2, “The human factor of the EOSC: Dissemination, Outreach and Community building” is on the following two:

- Build an active stakeholder community of EOSC supporters in each country
- Coordinate with other initiatives to achieve harmonisation for an inclusive EOSC

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/5726913>

Additionally, WP2 is constantly liaising with all the other WPs, providing them with communication and dissemination support for their activities and results.

1.2 Stakeholders Analysis and Targeted Messaging

For an in-depth analysis of the EOSC-Pillar stakeholders, please see D2.2 EOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement plan [D2.2], and its follow-up, D2.5 “EOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report” [D2.5]. What is outlined here is an update to the preliminary analysis in the previous deliverable.

1.2.1 New Relevant EOSC Projects

Since the last Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report, a number of new relevant projects have been launched such as: EOSC Future, the INFRAEOSC-07 projects: C-SCALE, Reliance, OpenAIRE, EGI-ACE, DICE, and the first EOSC projects funded under the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2021-2022 such as FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT, EOSC-FOCUS, and Skills4EOSC.

Where relevant, joint activities were organised such as the joint January 2022 webinar organised with DICE, the July 2021 national catalogues workshop and May 2022 policies workshop with EOSC Future. As the project is now at an advanced stage in its timeline, the focus was on disseminating the results produced aiming for their future uptake.

1.2.2 Developments in the EOSC Governance

During the reporting period, the EOSC Association AISBL had consolidated its activities further. Advisory Groups, each with its Task Forces that work on specific topics, provide guidelines and direction on the development of EOSC.

Towards the end of the period, a few of EOSC-Pillar’s Key Exploitable Results were mapped² by the EOSC Association to the work of their Advisory Group Task Forces ensuring EOSC-Pillar’s input to their work. EOSC-Pillar was also present at the EOSC Symposium 2022 in Prague, Czechia coordinating the organisation of a joint booth for the EOSC Regional Projects showcasing its main results and presented as part of the session “[EOSC engagement at regional level](#)”.

1.2.3 National Initiatives and Engagement at a National-Level

The reporting period also saw national initiatives reaching a higher level of maturity or organisation. Collaboration was seen with national initiatives such as the EOSC Support Office Austria, Italy’s ICDI, Germany’s NFDI and the Collège EOSC-France.

² Ilaria Nardello, Ari Asmi, René Buch, & Erik-Jan Bos. (2022). Delivering for EOSC - Key Exploitable Results of Horizon 2020 EOSC-related Projects (FULL Report). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7401539>

For the EOSC Support Office Austria, EOSC-Pillar supported in its establishment having supported the development of the Memorandum of Understanding which was the basis of their cooperation. Effort was also provided to Working Groups through UNIVIE and the national initiatives survey outputs for Austria helped identify its stakeholders and its first benchmark insights.

For Belgium in particular, it was necessary to monitor the developments and foster a network of key players on a regional level due to the federated way that open science is coordinated in the country.

For ICDI, EOSC-Pillar's Italian partners made up its first collaborators. Through knowledge and networks within EOSC-Pillar, ICDI monitored developments in the EOSC Association and shadow working groups that mirror the EOSC Association's Advisory Groups allow for the synchronisation of national developments with those in the EOSC. Italian-language training webinars were also organised with ICDI and other national entities.

For France and Germany, EOSC-Pillar supported the organisation of national EOSC events along with the Collège EOSC-France and NFDI promoting EOSC on a national level.

The EOSC-Pillar Ambassadors Programme was also rolled out across the five countries to increase familiarity with EOSC on an institutional level.

2 EOSC-Pillar Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Report

2.1 Campaigns

Seven communication campaigns for EOSC-Pillar were identified and described in D2.2 “EOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan” [D2.2], providing WP2 with a general framework for its activities. The full list of activities and KPIs within the campaigns are described in D2.2 with the updates as of M35 added in this section. Status and achievements of campaigns as of M18 can be viewed in D2.5³.

2.1.1 Campaign 1: Showcasing Diverse Use Cases & Community-Driven Pilots

This campaign promoted the rich set of use cases and pilots resulting from the national initiatives’ buy in to EOSC. This includes the nine initial use cases that are part of WP6’s description of work in addition to the new services collected in T6.10. As mentioned, the full list of activities and KPIs within the campaigns are described in D2.2 “EOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan” [D2.2].

Campaign 1 officially began in M18, building on the tangible results from EOSC-Pillar use cases, and accompanying their evolution through the project lifetime.

Trust-IT – as WP2 leader – supported all campaigns with key partners on each specific topic.

Duration: 31 December 2020 – 31 December 2022

Key Partners: CNRS, KIT

Activities Updates

- Created informative pages for each of the use cases⁴.
- Supported the publication and promotion of use case videos⁵.
- Published downloadable factsheets presenting each use case on Zenodo⁶.
- Published dedicated posters on each use case for the Final Conference
 - Use case 1 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7156748>
 - Use case 2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7194818>
 - Use case 3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7228220>
 - Use case 4 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7228091>
 - Use case 5 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7156780>
 - Use case 6 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051283>
 - Use case 7 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225815>
 - Use case 8 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225818>

³ [D2.5] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4453060>

⁴ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/eosc-pillar-launches-national-initiatives-survey>

⁵ <https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PL7O0ENAs2ZbLG1gLPZvY0dpgJwVWiK5Lz>

⁶ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/see-eosc-action-download-eosc-pillar-use-case-factsheets>

- Use case 9 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7194818>
- New services from open call <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225788>
- Supported use case teams in the production of materials for third party events.

Figure 1: Example images from Campaign 1 activities

2.1.2 Campaign 2: Policy and Legal Framework Recommendations

This campaign highlighted EOSC-Pillar’s contribution to creating sustainable services in EOSC through effective business models used by national initiatives.

In the second half of the project, campaign 2 mainly focused on the production of materials related to D4.1 Legal and Policy framework and federation blueprint, which was released as an updated version D4.6 in September 2021⁷.

The document then provided the basis for new materials, which WP2 has designed and promoted in support of WP4: a checklist and a recommendations document. This constituted the core of Campaign 2 in the final year of the project.

Activities Updates

- Publication of D4.6 Legal and Policy Framework and Federation Blueprint on Zenodo.

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647948>

- Production of two versions of the checklist for Legal Compliance Guidelines for Researchers.
 - Interactive digital version⁸
 - Printable version⁹
- Production of the Italian version of the checklist in collaboration with WP4
 - Interactive digital version¹⁰
 - Printable version¹¹
- Production of the downloadable booklet “Recommendations for Legal and Policy Harmonisation of Open and FAIR Science in the EU”
- Creation of dedicated webpages for these results
 - Checklist¹²
 - Recommendations¹³
- Organisation of joint workshop in May 2022¹⁴ “National Policies relevant to EOSC deployment”, with other the other H2020 projects involved in the INFRAEOSC-05 collaboration, also resulting in:
 - A post-event report¹⁵.
 - A post-event video¹⁶.

KPIs as of November 2022

- D4.6 Legal and Policy Framework and Federation Blueprint
 - 708 views
 - 485 downloads
- EOSC-Pillar Legal Compliance Guidelines for Researchers: a Checklist
 - 795 views (digital)
 - 573 downloads (digital)
 - 390 views (print)
 - 338 downloads (print)
- Recommendations for Legal and Policy Harmonisation of Open and FAIR Science in the EU
 - 863 views
 - 391 downloads
- National Policies relevant to EOSC deployment workshop
 - 100 online and on-site participants
 - Report views 487
 - Report downloads 259

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6327668>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6327691>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7152103>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7152093>

¹² <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/legal-compliance-guidelines-researchers-checklist>

¹³ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/recommendations-legal-policy-harmonisation-open-fair-science-eu>

¹⁴ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/workshop-national-policies-relevant-eosc-deployment>

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6584214>

¹⁶ https://youtu.be/Aw_QCS0VcT0

Duration: 31 December 2019 – 31 December 2022

Key Partners: KIT, INFN, CNR, CNRS, GARR

Figure 2: The two key dissemination documents from Campaign 2 activities

2.1.3 Campaign 3: Communicating the National Initiatives Survey

The campaign for the National Initiatives Survey took place in the first half of the project, and has been reported in D2.5 Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report¹⁷.

This campaign contributed to communicating the outcomes and insights that came out from the National Initiatives Surveys conducted by WP3, ultimately collected in D3.1 “Summary report of the EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey”¹⁸.

KPIs as of November 2022

- Summary report of the EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey
 - 1332 views
 - 967 downloads

Duration: 30 September 2019 - 30 June 2020

Key Partners: UNIVIE, KIT, CNRS

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4453060>

¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3937318>

2.1.4 Campaign 4: Support for Onboarding Services

This campaign supported EOSC-Pillar activities for onboarding services into EOSC in collaboration with WP4 and WP7, with a particular focus on the dissemination of D4.4 “National Service Registry Prototype” and D7.1 “Guidelines and recommendations for the technical integration of resources and services in the EOSC”.

This campaign also included the production of explanatory videos about EOSC and the EOSC Portal, which were released in 2022.

Activities Updates

- News about key steps in the project
 - Italian service registry prototype¹⁹
 - Maturity of EOSC-Pillar services²⁰
 - Guidelines and recommendations²¹
- Joint workshop on 5 July 2022 with EOSC Enhance, EOSC Future, and EOSC regional projects Workshop: Incorporating National and Thematic Service and Resource Catalogues into the EOSC²²
- Video tutorials
 - EOSC Federated AAI²³
 - Why should you trust EOSC Portal resources?²⁴
 - Join the development of EOSC²⁵

KPIs as of November 2022

- D7.1 Guidelines and Recommendations for the Technical Integration of Resources and Services in the EOSC
 - 115 views
 - 85 downloads

Duration: 31 March 2020 - 30 June 2021

Key Partners: INFN, KIT

¹⁹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/first-national-service-registry-prototype-developed-eosc-pillar-italian-community>

²⁰ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/assessing-maturity-eosc-pillar-services>

²¹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/guidelines-recommendations-technical-integration-resources-services-eosc>

²² <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/incorporating-national-thematic-service-resource-catalogues-eosc-portal>

²³ <https://youtu.be/71pv7zZRB3k>

²⁴ <https://youtu.be/F4oST9VdaxI>

²⁵ <https://youtu.be/7SL6NBjyrX8>

Figure 3: Example images from Campaign 4 activities

2.1.5 Campaign 5: Promoting the Open Call for Services

As outlined in D2.2 [D2.2], this campaign showcased the services that were awarded in the EOSC-Pillar Open Call, which was carried out between December 2020 and February 2021. 5 services received support from the EOSC-Pillar team and 3 of them were also onboarded into the EOSC Portal.

Activities Updates

- Webpage dedicated to the Open Call²⁶.
- News on new services resulting from the Open Call²⁷.
- Page on the new services sourced through the Open Call²⁸.
- Factsheet introducing the services: flyer²⁹ and poster³⁰ formats.

KPIs as of November 2022

- 178 page views on general page
- 96 page views on application form
- 9 applications
- Factsheet on Zenodo, as flyer and poster

²⁶ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/open-call-thematic-service-providers>

²⁷ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/six-applicants-awarded-eosc-pillar-open-call-thematic-service-providers>

²⁸ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/new-thematic-services-eosc-pillar-open-call>

²⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6726228>

³⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225788>

- 65 views
- 48 downloads

Duration: 28 February 2021 - 30 June 2022

Key Partners: GARR, KIT

Figure 4: Example images from Campaign 5 activities

2.1.6 Campaign 6: Communications Support for Stakeholder Engagement Activities

Through this campaign, WP2 has given visibility to the EOSC-Pillar community and to its growing relations with the wider landscape of EOSC-related projects across borders and disciplines.

This campaign ran through the entire duration of the project and kept track of all communications activities, including the management of the EOSC-Pillar website. More details on specific activities can be found in section 2.3 on Horizontal Activities.

A crucial element of this campaign was the **EOSC-Pillar Ambassadors Programme**³¹, carried out in 2021 and 2022 as a response to the survey results that showed low awareness of EOSC across certain segments. Task 2.3 produced materials on core topics such as Open Science, the FAIR principles, and EOSC, in collaboration with Task 2.1, to be distributed to representatives (the “EOSC Ambassadors”) of End Users (such as researchers) and Implementers (such as decision-makers at research infrastructures, or universities) communities, involving stakeholders and facilitating the uptake of these principles across disciplines and countries.

An important output of this campaign is the production of materials in the different EOSC-Pillar national languages (Dutch, French, German, Italian).

Key Activities Updates

- Monthly updates of webpage on EOSC-Pillar community featuring animated and interactive infographics on the EOSC-Pillar community and composition³².
- Management of events section on the website listing all the EOSC-Pillar organised webinars, workshops, as well as other relevant events EOSC-Pillar is involved in³³.
- Communications kit for the EOSC Ambassadors Programme³⁴.
- Stories Of Data: Open.Science.Talk³⁵ – The podcast series which was published between April and December 2022.
- EOSC-Pillar Final Conference – 25-27 October 2022 in Paris, France³⁶.
- Annual reports
 - First <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4288472>
 - Second <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5726913>
- 3 total workshops
- 10 total webinars

KPIs as of November 2022

- 3129 stakeholders in database
- 6300 combined video views on YouTube
- 30 inquiries received via Ambassadors Programme contact form
- 71% average attendance rate at webinars (out of registered participants)
- 114 participants in final event

Duration: 31 July 2019 – 31 December 2022

Key Partners: GARR, INFN, Trust-IT, UNIVIE

³¹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/ambassadors-programme>

³² <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/eosc-pillar-community>

³³ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events>

³⁴ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/ambassadors-programme>

³⁵ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/stories-data-open-science-podcast>

³⁶ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/final-conference>

Figure 5: Example images from Campaign 6 activities

2.1.7 Campaign 7: Supporting the Promotion of FAIR Culture

This campaign supported all activities related to the promotion of FAIR culture across the five EOSC-Pillar countries in different research communities, carried out in coordination with WP5.

WP2 also supported WP5 in the dissemination of the **EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue**³⁷.

Activities Updates

- RDM Training and Support Catalogue page
 - Nov 2020 Webinar³⁸
- Training activities in collaboration with other EOSC-related initiatives
 - Nov 2020 – Open Science e Covid-19 (Italian language, with EOSC-Life, RDA, OpenAIRE, Elixir Italy, CNR)³⁹
 - Nov 2020 – Corso di formazione Praticare l’Open Science nelle scienze della Terra e dell’Ambiente (with EC, OpenAIRE, CNR, EPOS, INGV)⁴⁰

³⁷ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/web/eoscpillartrainingandsupport/catalogue>

³⁸ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-eosc-pillar-rdm-training-and-support-catalogue>

³⁹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-open-science-covid-19-collaborare-pandemia>

⁴⁰ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/corso-formazione-praticare-open-science-scienze-terra-ambiente>

- Apr 2021 – Collaborare per contrastare la pandemia (Italian language, COVID-19 Data Portal)⁴¹
- Jun 2021 – Instructor training (with EOSC-Synergy, FAIRsFAIR, UGent)⁴²
- Sep 2021 – Open Science e Covid-19 (Italian language, with EOSC-Life, RDA, OpenAIRE, Elixir Italy, CNR)⁴³
- Jan 2022 FAIR Data Management Gaps and Solutions (with DICE)⁴⁴
- Feb 2022 – Teaching and training FAIR to HEI in Italy. National Roadshow in Italy (with FAIRsFAIR and ICDI)⁴⁵
- Mar 2022 - Practical course on FAIR Data Stewardship in Life Science (with EOSC-Life)⁴⁶

KPIs as of November 2022

- RDM Training and Support Catalogue
 - 261 page views
 - 54 webinar attendees

Duration: 30 June 2020 – 31 December 2022

Key Partners: CINES, CNR, Fraunhofer, GARR, UGent

⁴¹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/collaborare-contrastare-la-pandemia-un-webinar-sul-covid-19-data-portal-italiano>

⁴² <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/instructor-training-online-workshop>

⁴³ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-open-science-covid-19-dati-epidemiologici>

⁴⁴ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/fair-data-management-gaps-and-solutions>

⁴⁵ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/teaching-training-fair-hei-italy-national-roadshow>

⁴⁶ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/practical-course-fair-data-stewardship-life-science>

2.2 The InfraEOSC-05 Collaboration

Towards the last stretch of the project, EOSC-Pillar remained committed to the InfraEOSC-05 collaboration with EOSC- Synergy, EOSC-Nordic, NI4OS-Europe, ExPaNDS, EOSC Secretariat.eu, and FAIRsFAIR through cross-project task forces: National Policies and Governance, Training and Skills, Communication and Events, FAIR, Service Onboarding, and Landscaping. The following activities were carried out:

- **EOSC Association Board Interviews with Country Perspectives:** Following the first elections of a new set of EOSC Association Board Members, EOSC-Pillar conducted interviews from the members coming from EOSC-Pillar countries. This idea was shared in the Communication and Events Task Force and was also carried out in the other projects. The interviews were then collected and showcased at the EOSC Association: <https://eosc.eu/news/eosc-association-regional-national-communities-interviews-board>
- **2nd EOSC-Pillar Workshop:** Leveraging the collaboration with the other regional projects, EOSC-Pillar organised a workshop on “Onboarding National Catalogues through/to the EOSC Portal - A Roadmap”. The workshop provided the regional projects with a forum to synchronise with the EOSC Portal operators on onboarding national catalogues. See: <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/incorporating-national-thematic-service-resource-catalogues-eosc-portal>

- **Promotion of the Joint Workshop at the Open Science FAIR:** A workshop was co-organised with other INFRAEOSC-05 projects on 22 September 2021 as part of the Open Science FAIR programme titled “Let’s discuss about FAIRifying OS policies”: <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/open-science-fair-2021>
- **3rd EOSC-Pillar Workshop:** In collaboration with EOSC Synergy and other INFRAEOSC-05-b projects, we supported the organisation of the workshop “National Policies relevant to EOSC deployment – Status, gaps, and steps towards harmonisation”. Summary video and report are found here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Aw_QCS0VcT0

2.3 Horizontal Activities

2.3.1 Website

EOSC-Pillar’s website⁴⁷ represents the central digital hub for communication and engagement. Several new sections were incorporated since the initial version described in D2.2 [D2.2] and the revised one described in D2.5 [D2.5].

The current structure of the website can be seen in Figure 6: Sitemap below. The “News” and “Events” menu items have been merged into the “News & Events” menu item.

⁴⁷ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/>

Figure 6: Sitemap

2.3.1.1 Results pages

The “Results” menu item was moved to the top of the menu to be given higher priority as the end of the project approaches. This menu features seven pages, each focusing on specific aspects of the EOSC-Pillar project. These pages include an introduction, generally a video interview with experts of the area, and relevant links to additional results.

- National Initiatives Survey⁴⁸
- Survey Results ⁴⁹
- From National Initiatives to Transnational Services⁵⁰
- Establishing FAIR Data Services⁵¹
- Federated FAIR Data Space⁵²
- Horizontal Data Storage and Computing Services⁵³
- Dissemination, Outreach and Community Building⁵⁴

⁴⁸ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/eosc-pillar-national-initiatives-survey-work-package>

⁴⁹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/first-results-national-initiatives-survey>

⁵⁰ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/eosc-pillar-national-initiatives-transnational-services>

⁵¹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/establishing-fair-data-services>

⁵² <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/federated-fair-data-space-f2ds>

⁵³ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/horizontal-data-storage-and-computing-services>

⁵⁴ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/dissemination-outreach-and-community-building>

The EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey Work Package (WP3) designed and conducted a set of surveys to assess the state of the art of the Open Science landscapes in Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, and Italy.

To achieve its purpose and to gain a comprehensive picture of the European scientific infrastructure landscape, the WP3 team initiated about 2,000 questionnaires across the five EU Member States.

Initiatives were identified based on their name and activities with regard to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The questionnaires were addressed to four types of respondents: funding agencies, universities, research infrastructures, and infrastructures.

How the surveys will support the development of EOSC

To discuss and assess gaps, initiate necessary developments, start specific support measures and create opportunities, the survey data available will be the key factor for open research data and services. It also provided initial insights for the activities of EOSC Pillar's Work Package 4: "From National Initiatives to Transnational Services".

The leader of the National Initiatives Survey Work Package, **Udo Hübner** from German community, said:

"Our aim is to collect comprehensive data from multiple European countries to allow for evidence-based decision-making in shaping the future of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). There is a need to create a solid database and a comprehensive picture of the research infrastructure landscape. By entering this course, we deliver the basis for steering policies which support developing the European Infrastructure landscape for open research data."

Survey Methodology and Questionnaire

The full edition for scientific use of the questionnaire and methodology is freely available on the EOSC Pillar website. Please see our [FAQ](#) to learn more.

The EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey Roadmap

3 October 2019
EOSC Pillar launched its National Initiatives Survey (WP3) to assess the state of the art of the Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The survey is a key factor for open research data and services. It also provided initial insights for the activities of EOSC Pillar's Work Package 4: "From National Initiatives to Transnational Services".

30 October 2019 / November 2019
To allow institutions and researchers to better understand the aim of these surveys and help them to answer properly, EOSC Pillar's team has organized 3 webinars in the five languages in France, Italy, and Germany. You can watch these webinars here.

April 2020
The results of the survey

Webinar on the National Initiatives Survey results on the 3rd of April. You can watch the recording and download the slides from the presentation.

Summer 2020
Full report of the National Initiatives Survey

October 2020
The document of the National Initiatives Survey was published on EOSC Pillar's website. You can find it on [EOSC Pillar's website](#).

Don't miss any updates, subscribe to our newsletter and become a part of our EOSC-Pillar community. Follow us on [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#).

"The Data layer: establishing FAIR data services at the national and transnational level" Work Package (WP3) reduces technical, societal and organisational barriers to ensure research data considered in EOSC-Pillar is FAIR.

The goal is achieved by addressing the following objectives:

- Develop an innovative set of services for a Federated FAIR Data Space (F2DS), starting from the context of existing research data repositories.
- Set up support and training activities, following the dissemination and adoption of FAIR practices for research data management.
- Build, sustain and appropriate domain-specific ontologies and related metadata as the main basis for cross-domain interoperability.

Check out the existing EOSC Pillar Research Data Management training and support catalogue:

More WPS Services

To ease the access to the current state of work, we provide in the table below the list of services together with the partners hosting the services, the access URL, and a short description.

DISCLAIMER:
Please be aware that these services might not be available continuously because they are periodically updated. In the case where links are not working please contact the email of the related contact person to obtain information on the status of the service(s):

- Clare Beuchon (clare.beuchon@cea.fr) for CNRS hosted services
- Benardita Candela (benardita.candela@europe.ec.europa.eu) for the DG Science hosted services

Service	Hosted by	Description
FAIR DataSpace API	CNRS	API to access the content of the FAIR DataSpace
FAIR DataSpace user interface	CNRS	User interface to access the content of the FAIR DataSpace
FAIR DataSpace metadata	CNRS	User interface for repository registration
FAIR DataSpace search	CNRS	Engine metadata in rich with specific query language
EOSC Pillar catalogue	EOSC Pillar (by consensus)	The actual research environment is available at (for authorized users)
EOSC Pillar catalogue - public use	EOSC Pillar (by consensus)	The publicly available version of the catalogue

Don't miss any updates, register for our newsletter and become a part of our EOSC-Pillar community. Keep in touch with us follow us on [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#).

Figure 7: Examples of Results pages

2.3.1.2 Zenodo Community

In the summer of 2020, EOSC-Pillar also launched its Zenodo Community⁵⁵, where key documents such as public deliverables and milestones can be found. In November 2022 the community counts a total of 67 published deliverables

2.3.2 EOSC-Pillar Ambassadors Programme

During the last 18 months of the EOSC-Pillar project, Task 2.3 focused on the EOSC-Pillar Ambassadors Programme. The goal of this programme was to firstly raise awareness about EOSC and secondly have people spread the word about it. The Ambassadors Programme aimed to support everyone willing to promote Open Science and the benefits of EOSC to their community, be it individual researchers or people working at research supporting or funding organisations. The goal was to establish a community of EOSC Ambassadors. Therefore, a complete set of informative materials and multimedia content was created and used for this purpose. The material included flyers, posters, presentations as well as videos and a podcast series: "Stories of Data – Open.Science.Talk". All content can be found on the [EOSC-Pillar Website](#) and might be adapted, shared, and reused.

⁵⁵ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/eosc-pillar-community-launched-zenodo>

2.3.2.1 Materials

The following materials were created as part of the Ambassadors Programme

Item	Results (06-2022)	Results (11-2022)	Link
Poster - September 2021	273 views 225 downloads	325 views 278 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5511634#.Yt6afHZBw2w
Poster - French version	135 views 75 downloads	156 views 92 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5752181#.Yt6afHZBw2w
Poster – Dutch version	70 views 26 downloads	92 views 48 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5789033#.Yt6afXZBw2w
Poster – Italian version	99 views 39 downloads	123 views 51 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5789497#.Yt6afnZBw2w
Poster – German version	62 views 43 downloads	198 views 54 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5877192#.Yt6afnZBw2w
Presentation for Researchers	183 views 66 downloads	243 views 99 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5735368#.Yt6ahXZBw2w
Presentation for Organisations	125 views 42 downloads	175 views 23 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5735341#.Yt6ahnZBw2w
General Flyer	89 views 76 downloads	137 views 119 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5524733#.Yt6aiHZBw2w
Flyer for Researchers	229 views 166 downloads	346 views 229 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/6794049#.Yt6aiHZBw2x
Flyer for Researchers – Italian Version	54 views 32 downloads	65 views 40 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5844457#.Yt6ainZBw2w
Flyer for Researchers – Dutch Version	27 views 18 downloads	46 views 31 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/6341723#.Yt6ai3ZBw2w
Flyer for Researchers – French Version	43 views 26 downloads	65 views 40 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/6367806#.Yt6ai3ZBw2w
Flyer for Researchers – German Version	63 views 55 downloads	84 views 75 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/6419123#.Yt6ajHZBw2w
Flyer for Organisations	134 views 87 downloads	207 views 144 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/5524755#.Yt6ajnZBw2w
Use Case Flyer: FAIR Data for Earth Sciences	75 views 61 downloads	163 views 113 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/6584737#.Yt6aj3ZBw2w

2.3.2.2 Podcast

Two seasons of podcasts were created. The first one in cooperation with the SSHOC project and the second discussing the present and future of EOSC with a focus on EOSC-Pillar contributions. From the vision - to the mission - to the reality. The aim of the podcast is to

make EOSC more tangible and to support researchers in the implementation of Open Science and FAIR Data. This objective is achieved by presenting practical examples and introducing some of the EOSC Community's tools and services. The podcasts can be accessed on Spotify and Anchor. The full list of recorded podcast episodes is available [here](#).

Episode	Date	Plays 11-2022	Link
Season 1 – EOSC-Pillar and SSHOC			
Pilot: Welcome to the show!	12-04-2022	60	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/Pilot-Welcome-to-the-show-e1h2svg
EOSC - Why and How?	19-04-2022	50	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/EOSC--Why-and-How-e1hcj9j
EOSC - How to use it?	26-04-2022	38	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/EOSC--How-to-use-it-e1hmg1u
EOSC - Let's get practical! Vol. 1	03-05-2022	47	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/EOSC--Lets-get-practical--Vol--1-e1i0m89
EOSC - Who needs to do what?	10-05-2022	31	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/EOSC--Who-needs-to-do-what-e1iau76
SSHOC - United in Diversity	31-05-2022	19	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/SSHOC---United-in-Diversity-e1ja71c
SSHOCing Tools for the Job	07-06-2022	15	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/SSHOCing-Tools-for-the-Job-e1jk49i
EOSC - An Open Future	14-06-2022	28	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/EOSC--An-Open-Future-e1jnt1n
Season 2 – EOSC-Pillar			
EOSC - Connecting research services	06-09-2022	28	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/EOSC--Connecting-research-services-e1nelld
FAIR Data for Earth Sciences	13-09-2022	23	https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/FAIR-Data-for-Earth-Sciences-e1norjm
Data Reuse Behavior - Researchers Study	06-12-2022	N/A yet	
Business Models for Open Science IT Services	13-12-2022	N/A yet	
Ambassadors for Open Science	20-12-2022	N/A yet	

2.3.3 Social media channels

The EOSC-Pillar social media channels include [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#). The social channels provide an instant form of communication with community members.

The social channels have been used as a sounding board. Through a scheduled and consistent content calendar, the outreach team has ensured continual visibility of the project’s activities such as events, webinars, news posts, and announcements. Social media also supported community building by providing a path from seeing the social messages to converting as an engaged stakeholder. The following figure summarises the main statistics and analytics related to the overall community on LinkedIn and Twitter in November 2022:

Twitter (total followers = 1,260 as of November 2022)

LinkedIn (total followers = 569 as of November 2022)

Figure 8: Selected social media analytics

2.3.4 Contact Database

An EOSC-Pillar Community database has been set up to keep track of how the community is building and to categorise relevant stakeholders.

Contacts are acquired via subscriptions to the newsletter, registration via the web platform, registration to EOSC-Pillar webinars, participation at events, social media networks connections, partners' efforts (such as the National Initiatives Survey) as well as synergies and strategic collaborations.

An overview of the EOSC-Pillar Community, updated monthly, can be found on the EOSC-Pillar website⁵⁶. Please also find a snapshot of several relevant KPIs in section 2.4.2 of this document.

⁵⁶ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/eosc-pillar-community>

Figure 9: The EOSC-Pillar Community

2.3.5 Newsletter

Another key channel to inform stakeholders of the project’s activities, is the newsletter which EOSC-Pillar has regularly sent to its contact database via email.

As part of the strategy of the EOSC-Pillar, emails have only been sent to relevant contacts when relevant updates were available to share. This principle was followed to reduce the chances of sending emails simply to “meet quotas” and ensuring that stakeholders only receive valuable information at the right time and are not overwhelmed with too frequent direct contacts. The following image provides a visual example of an email newsletter which reflects the project’s brand identity and includes a clear call to action at the end and is representative of the main structure used for all communications.

Figure 10: An example of a newsletter

Over the course of the project a total of **21 newsletters** were sent showing positive results in terms of both open (on average 41%) and click rates (on average 15%).

2.3.6 Interviews with the EOSC Association board of directors

Among the many pieces of news and articles that have been published on the EOSC-Pillar website, a series has attracted interest from across the wider EOSC community.

In the context of the INFRAEOSC-05 collaboration, EOSC-Pillar had proposed and led a series of interviews with Directors of the EOSC Association⁵⁷, kicking it off with three interviews to the Directors from Germany, France and Italy in Q1 2021, who were just elected at the end of 2020 in the first official EOSC Association General Assembly.

The other regional projects and EOSCsecretariat.eu went on to interview the remaining directors, based on their geographical coverage.

Title	Date	Views 11-2022	Link
€900m German Open Science Initiative NFDI Progresses as EOSC Association Gears Up An interview with Klaus Tochtermann, ZBW	22-02-2021	129	https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/german-open-science-initiative-nfdi-progresses-eosc-association
From Policy to Practice: France CNRS launches Open Data Research Directorate and participation in EOSC Association thrives An interview with Suzanne Dumouchel, CNRS	01-08-2021	70	https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/policy-practice-france-cnrs-open-data-research-directorate-eosc-association-dumouchel
Turning points for Open Science in Italy: national OS plan advances with ICDI An interview with Marialuisa Lavitrano, UNIMIB	08-03-2021	68	https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/turning-points-open-science-italy-national-os-plan-advances-icdi
Getting to know NFDI, the German National Research Data Infrastructure, with York Sure-Vetter An interview with York Sure-Vetter, NFDI Director (extra interview)	21-07-2021	55	https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/nfdi-german-national-research-data-infrastructure-york-sure-vetter

⁵⁷ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/eosc-association-regional-national-communities-interviews-board>

2.3.7 Videos

WP2 has supported the project in the design, production and promotion of video materials. These included several types ranging from interviews to tutorials and post-event videos. Videos have helped disseminate key project contents such as use case stories, instructions on how to use EOSC Portal services, project events, and more.

The videos have also been arranged into thematic playlists on the EOSC-Pillar YouTube channel. Over the lifetime of the project, the channel has collected 6.4k views as of November 2022.

Video	Date	Views (11-2022)	Link
EOSC-Pillar use cases			
Use case 1 - Procedures and services to enforce data provenance for thematic communities and beyond	04-06-2021	84	https://youtu.be/uV-Gi2pouOw
Use case 2 - Agile FAIR data for environment and earth system communities	04-06-2021	78	https://youtu.be/D8JsFpJflv0
Use case 3 - Integration of data repositories into EOSC based on communities' approaches	04-06-2021	137	https://youtu.be/iaiFHpj2HgQ
Use case 4 - Software source code preservation, reference and access	04-06-2021	30	https://youtu.be/QrgAsRXWTkE
Use case 5 - Proof of Concept to link HAL publications and NAKALA repository	04-06-2021	160	https://youtu.be/DxZ8H0Q0vHU
Use case 6 - Reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics community	04-06-2021	86	https://youtu.be/WZey8XrCp1l
Use case 7 - Suitable data formats for seismological big data provisioning via web services	04-06-2021	38	https://youtu.be/57kkGkw8-mA
Use case 8 - Definition of big datasets at seismological data centres based on RDA recommendations	04-06-2021	14	https://youtu.be/4Oso80i9rME
Use case 9 - Integrating heterogeneous data on cultural heritage	04-06-2021	57	https://youtu.be/0NBHT2f5Vqk
Use cases overview: Open Science practices with EOSC-Pillar	23-12-2022	N/A	N/A
Interviews			

Video	Date	Views (11-2022)	Link
Fulvio Galeazzi (GARR Consortium), Project Manager of EOSC-Pillar	31-10-2019	89	https://youtu.be/IZohEnXCqZY
WP2 - Rob Carrillo (Trust-IT) Manager, The Human Factor of the EOSC	31-10-2019	109	https://youtu.be/2_c0gxs7m0M
WP3 - Lisa Hönegger (UNIVIE) Manager, National Initiatives Survey	31-10-2019	174	https://youtu.be/62zozwz91yCE
WP4 - Federica Tanlongo (GARR) Manager, From National Initiatives to Transnational Services	31-10-2019	159	https://youtu.be/gVBnZX01WUc
WP5 - Adham Hashibon (Fraunhofer IWM) Manager, The Data Layer	31-10-2019	195	https://youtu.be/Xr77x6Jgmk
WP6 - Frédéric Huynh (IRD) Manager EOSC in action: Use cases and community-driven pilots	31-10-2019	118	https://youtu.be/ReKZd9wCfzs
WP7 Volker Beckmann (CNRS/IN2P3): The infrastructure layer	31-10-2019	73	https://youtu.be/Nai48DLYU5Y
EOSC-Pillar at the EOSC Symposium 2019 - An Interview with Fulvio Galeazzi	20-12-2019	62	https://youtu.be/wdjAngzfpA4
EOSC-Pillar at the EOSC Symposium 2019 - An interview with Yann Le Franc	20-12-2019	73	https://youtu.be/xNsKtf9PKi0
What is Open Science and how does society benefit from it? - Insights from Austrian research experts	16-11-2020	286	https://youtu.be/AdYUJn3ApyQ
What is data? - Interviews with French researchers	17-01-2022	521	https://youtu.be/J7nkClygNng
What are the impacts of FAIRification? - Interviews with French researchers	17-01-2022	122	https://youtu.be/JxDm4lmw8Vs
The Data Paper: 1 – Definition	26-04-2022	312	https://youtu.be/dl-3aYBbu7Y
The Data Paper: 2 - Ecosystem	26-04-2022	130	https://youtu.be/kGtu1g7G6U8
The Data Paper: 3 - Impact	26-04-2022	121	https://youtu.be/GyGPMulcmGU
The Federated FAIR Data Space and EOSC - An interview with Yann Le Franc, CINES	19-09-2022	22	https://youtu.be/90EpHynNTTQ
Connecting EOSC-Pillar to the wider EOSC ecosystem - An interview with	19-09-	6	https://youtu.be/Yu8j

Video	Date	Views (11-2022)	Link
Olivier Rouchon, CINES	2022		hShUtics
Tutorials, demos			
EOSC-Pillar Use case 6 demo - Galaxy	30-09-2021	46	https://youtu.be/SK9C_MWz6Yk
FAIRification of data in mass	18-10-2021	148	https://youtu.be/hyggpLsCJMY
CIDOC CRM Ontology for sharing archaeological data	07-12-2021	323	https://youtu.be/0ZF34982h-M
The EOSC federated AAI: How can it help you	27-04-2022	201	https://youtu.be/71pv7zZRB3k
The ELAN Software for social sciences and humanities	11-05-2022	166	https://youtu.be/AIJDOSAzL_I
Share, publish and enhance your scientific data with Nakala	19-09-2022	22	https://youtu.be/haMpOdYQGdA
Why should you trust EOSC Portal resources?	24-10-2022	45	https://youtu.be/F4oST9VdaxI
Join the development of EOSC	24-10-2022	56	https://youtu.be/7SL6NBjyrX8
Post-event videos			
Strasbourg 4 May 2022 Workshop: National Policies relevant to EOSC deployment status	18-07-2022	106	https://youtu.be/Aw_QCS0VcT0
EOSC-Pillar Final Conference: Building an EOSC from National Contributions	14-10-2022	74	https://youtu.be/2u6q4s6CrLM

2.3.8 Events and Webinars

2.3.8.1 Webinars

With COVID-19 still having an impact for the earlier half of the reporting period, EOSC-Pillar continued to run online events such as webinars.

Initially, EOSC-Pillar had planned for 10 webinars, but in the end delivered 14.

WP2 provided technical support, promotion, and live tweeting for all webinars and makes the eventual public recordings and slides available on the event pages of the EOSC-Pillar website.

Aside from the attendance of the live broadcast, the webinar recordings are also consumed on-demand. For this reason, we have listed the views as of the end of November 2022.

N.	Webinar	Date	Video & Result
1	Coming together to map the national landscape analysis on EOSC between 5 relevant projects with Member States ⁵⁸	11-10-2019	https://youtu.be/i8Mly99V0-g Attendees: 109, Views: 91
2	EOSC-Pillar's National Initiatives Survey for Germany ⁵⁹	28-10-2019	https://youtu.be/e-LHrsvpPs8 Views: 39
3	EOSC-Pillar's National Initiatives Survey for Italy ⁶⁰	28-10-2019	https://youtu.be/4NQONAM0kkg Views: 33
4	EOSC-Pillar's National Initiatives Survey for France ⁶¹	04-11-2019	https://youtu.be/0X8MRzAji3M Views: 48
5	National Initiatives Survey Results ⁶²	03-04-2020	https://youtu.be/ddf48Yyw_UI Live attendees: 179, Views: 127
6	Synergies between Horizon and ESIF in EOSC Partnership ⁶³	20-07-2020	https://youtu.be/nTbUuSdR5Uk Live attendees: 63, Views: 131
7-10	Open Science e COVID-19 (series of 4) ⁶⁴	21-07-2020 16-11-2020 28-04-2021 28-09-2021	1: https://youtu.be/-hl3kXn6jVA Views: 254 2: https://youtu.be/f92ztechgc4 Views: 156 3: https://youtu.be/Y5wxAtYulo0 Views: 665 4: https://youtu.be/2fb6M0qxFeA Views: 136
11	The Role of Policies for a Sustainable EOSC ⁶⁵	27-10-2020	https://youtu.be/hFrMhuc3cco Live attendees: 42, Views: 79
12	EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue ⁶⁶	12-11-2020	https://youtu.be/CRbrrP5pOK0 Live attendees: 54, Views: 74
13	EOSC-Pillar Business Model Workshop	01-07-2021	https://youtu.be/OcEyJpkwCl8 Live attendees: 62, Views: 36

⁵⁸ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-coming-together-map-national-landscape-analysis-eosc-between-5-relevant-projects>

⁵⁹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-eosc-pillars-national-initiatives-survey-germany>

⁶⁰ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-eosc-pillars-national-initiatives-survey-italy>

⁶¹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-eosc-pillars-national-initiatives-survey-france>

⁶² <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-national-initiatives-survey-results>

⁶³ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-synergies-between-horizon-european-structural-investment-funds-eosc>

⁶⁴ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-covid-19-condivisione-dati-italia>

⁶⁵ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-role-policies-sustainable-eosc>

⁶⁶ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-eosc-pillar-rdm-training-and-support-catalogue>

14	Germany and EOSC for researchers	23-02-2022	https://youtu.be/BtF1DQ3FQsQ Live attendees: 140, Views: 104
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2.3.8.2 Visibility in Third-Party Events

EOSC-Pillar representatives have also taken part in many third-party events organised by key stakeholders in the EOSC environment, both at the European and national levels. Please find below the list of events that EOSC-Pillar representatives have joined as of November 2020.

	Event	Date	Venue
1	EOSC Jam session: Shaping the EOSC ecosystem synergies	6-7/12/2019	Turin
2	TNC 2019	17-19/06/2019	Tallinn
3	E-InfraCentral: Building Open Science in Europe: The road ahead for EU Member States and the EOSC community	20/06/2019	Tallinn
4	National Open Science policies and the implementation of the EOSC	05/07/2019	Rome
5	The 2019 conference of the Computational and Theoretical Chemistry	1-6/09/2019	Rome
6	EOSC Concertation Meeting	9-10/09/2019	Brussels
7	Open Science Fair	16-18/09/2019	Porto
8	RDA Plenary 14 / EOSC@RDA	21-24/10/2019	Helsinki
9	EOSC WG Sustainability Meeting	23/10/2019	Helsinki
10	Belgian Open Science: EOSC Initiatives	21/11/2019	Brussels
11	EOSC Symposium	25-28/11/2019	Budapest
12	Europeana 2019	27/11/2019	Lisbon
13	EOSC Coordination Days	28-29/11/2019	Budapest
14	EOSC-Pillar at the EOSC Day hosted by CNRS in Paris	22/01/2020	Paris
15	EOSC-Pillar at the 5th OANA network meeting in Vienna	23/01/2020	Vienna
16	European Dataverse Workshop 2020	23-24/01/2020	Tromsø
17	EOSC Café BMBWF	14/02/2020	Online
18	Invitation to EOSC Executive Board Meeting	28/02/2020	Brussels

19	EOSC Portal requirements gathering workshop	12/05/2020	Online
20	EOSC Consultation Day	18/05/2020	Online
21	EOSC-hub Week 2020	18-20/05/2020	Online
22	Austrian Repository Managers Network	07/07/2020	Online
23	1st WEBINAR: Covid-19 e condivisione dei dati: perché in Italia si fa troppo poco?	21/07/2020	Online
24	EOSC use cases Workshop by EOSCsecretariat / Networking	03/09/2020	Online
25	EUA Webinar: Universities and the European Open Science Cloud	04/09/2020	Online
26	ESOF 2020 - Research Evaluation and Incentives to boost Open Science and Research Careers	05/09/2020	Online
27	FAIR Data Austria Workshop	08/09/2020	Online
28	Open Access Tage	15-17/09/2020	Online
29	Open Access Forum	22/09/2020	Online
30	EOSC Portal Requirements Validation and Prioritisation Workshop	28/09/2020	Online
31	EOSC Landscape Final Validation Workshop	28-29/09/2020	Online
32	2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop	6-7/10/2020	Online
33	Open Access Week Belgium	20/10/2020	Online
34	Workshop on Training Resource Catalogue Interoperability	29/10/2020	Online
35	2nd WEBINAR - Open Science e COVID-19: Collaborare per contrastare la pandemia	16/11/2020	Online
36	EOSC Projects EXPO	16-19/11/2020	Online
37	Corso di formazione "Praticare l'Open Science nelle scienze della Terra e dell'ambiente"	24/11/2020	Online
38	JCAD2020 conference	03/12/2020	Online
39	French EOSC day	04/02/2021	Online
40	EOSC Portal API workshop with EOSC Enhance	03/03/2021	Online
41	Digitalisation of Research Data at EMMC 2021	03/03/2021	Online
42	EOSC-Pillar Day France	22/03/2021	Online
43	16th International Digital Curation Conference	19/04/2021	Online
44	Focused Group Training on Open Science &	19/04/2021	Online

	Research Data Management		
45	European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2021 (EGU)	28/04/2021	Vienna, online
46	3rd WEBINAR - Open Science e COVID-19: Collaborare per contrastare la pandemia	28/04/2021	Online
47	Tech Talk on the DKRZ CMIP6 Data Pool	18/05/2021	Hamburg, online
48	Webinar series on Digital Humanities organised by the University of Naples Federico II	20/05/2021	Online
49	FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Synergy and Ghent University Instructor Training Workshop	07-11/06/2021	Online
50	RDM Training and Support Catalogue (OpenScience FAIR)	21/09/2021	Online
51	WORKSHOP: Let's discuss about FAIRifying Open Science policies (Open Science FAIR)	22/12/2021	Online
52	4th WEBINAR - Open Science e COVID-19: Collaborare per contrastare la pandemia	28/09/2021	Online
53	e-IRG workshop under Slovenian presidency	01-02/12/2021	Online
54	JCAD2021	13-15/12/2021	Dijon
- 55	EOSC-Pillar DICE Webinar	31/01/2022	Online
56	FAIRsFAIR Italy Roadshow	09/02/2022	Online
57	Practical course on FAIR Data Stewardship in Life Science	02-11/03/2022	Online
58	Journées EOSC-France 2022	04-05/04/2022	Online
59	EOSC Providers Days	26-28/04/2022	Online
60	Workshop on National Policies relevant to EOSC deployment	04/05/2022	Strasbourg
61	ITRN meeting Provando e Riprovando	13/05/2022	Florence
62	TNC 2022	14-17/06/2022	Trieste, online
63	NI4OS regional event	28-29/09/2022	Budapest
64	EGI Conference 2022	20-22/09/2022	Prague
65	TPDL 2022	20-23/09/2022	Padua
66	JCAD 2022	10-12/10/2022	Dijon
67	EOSC Symposium 2022	14-17/11/2022	Prague
68	Marseille University - Open Science Course	01/12/2022	Marseille

Initially, the project had planned to take part in 80 third-party events, however, with COVID-19 a whole two-year lull on on-site events was observed and in the end the project was only able to secure visibility in a total of 68 events.

Despite this however, EOSC-Pillar was present in several regular closed meetings of the EOSC governance, representing the project position and for most of them, not only making EOSC-Pillar visible, but also actively contributing to their outputs. This includes regular meetings of the six EOSC Executive Board Working Groups, eight EOSC Association Advisory Group Task Forces and six INFRAEOSC-05 Collaboration Task Forces. Therefore, we believe that with 68 events coupled with our presence in the closed meetings of these 20 groups, we have provided adequate visibility to the project. Below are the various meetings where specific EOSC-Pillar representatives attended:

EOSC Executive Board Working Groups (2019-2020)

- **Architecture:** Tobias Weigel (DKRZ), Jerome Pansanel (CNRS), Tommaso Boccali (INFN), Paolo Manghi (CNR-ISTI), Andrea Ceccanti (INFN)
- **FAIR:** Stefano Cozzini (Area Science Park)
- **Landscape:** Paolo Budroni (UWien), Achim Streit (KIT), Volker Beckmann (CNRS)
- **Rules of Participation:** Pasquale Pagano (CNR)
- **Sustainability:** Federico Ruggieri (GARR), Paolo Budroni (UWien), Achim Streit (KIT), Volker Beckmann (CNRS)
- **Training & Skills:** Emma Lazzeri (CNR), Suzanne Dumouchel (CNRS)

EOSC Association Advisory Groups (2021-present)

- **Implementation of EOSC**
 - **PID Policy and Implementation:** Claudio Pisa (GARR)
 - **Researcher engagement and adoption:** Vincent Breton (CNRS-IN2P3), Federica Tanlongo (GARR)
 - **Rules of Participation (RoP) compliance monitoring:** Luciano Gaido (INFN), Odile Hologne (INRAE)
- **Technical Challenges**
 - **Infrastructures for quality research software:** Leonardo Candela (CNR), Violaine Louvet (CNRS)
- **Metadata and Data Quality**
 - **Semantic Interoperability:** Yann Le Franc (e-Science Data Factory, CINES)
- **Research Careers and Curricula**
 - **Upskilling countries to engage in EOSC:** Emma Lazzeri (GARR)
- **Sustaining EOSC**
 - **Financial Sustainability:** Laura Perini (INFN), Jean-Pierre Villotte (CNRS)
 - **Long-term data preservation:** Marcello Maggi (INFN), Riccardo Smareglia (INAF)

INFRAEOSC-05 Collaboration Task Forces:

- **Landscaping:** Jos Van Wezel (KIT), Volker Beckmann (CNRS), Lisa Hönegger (UNIVIE), Yann Le Franc (CINES), Sara Di Giorgio (GARR)
- **FAIR data and infrastructure:** Federica Tanlongo (GARR), Jos Van Wezel (KIT), Sara Di Giorgio (GARR), Olivier Rouchon (CINES)
- **Service Onboarding:** Federica Tanlongo (GARR), Leonardo Candela (CNR), Luciano Gaido (INFN), Fulvio Galeazzi (GARR)
- **National Policies and Governance:** Federica Tanlongo (GARR), Fulvio Galeazzi (GARR), Sara Di Giorgio (GARR), Volker Beckmann (CNRS), Jos Van Wezel (KIT), Nadina Foggetti (INFN), Netsanet Haile Gebreyesus
- **Training and Skills:** Emma Lazzeri (CNR), Inge Van Nieuwerburgh (Ugent)
- **Communications and Events:** Rob Carrillo (Trust-IT), Elis Bertazon (GARR), Federico Drago (Trust-IT)

2.3.8.3 Workshops

EOSC-Pillar organised a total of three workshops. EOSC-Pillar used this event format to advance its work or contribute to wider discussions happening at the European level and always sought to involve other projects as co-organisers to use these events to ensure coordination with parallel efforts in other counterpart projects.

Event	Date	Location	Attendees
Workshop 1: Policy Landscape in Europe	20-05-2020	Online	188
Workshop 2: Incorporating Catalogues into EOSC	05-07-2021	Online	45
Workshop 3: National policies relevant to EOSC deployment	04-05-2022	Strasbourg	100+

2.3.8.4 EOSC-Pillar Final Event

The EOSC-Pillar Final Event, held at the National Library of France from 25-27 October 2022 showcased the main results of the project at its end. The final event was structured with the first part providing a high-level overview of some of the work areas of the project followed by shorter, but more focused sessions on a specific major result.

With all presentations and recordings published online, those interested in EOSC-Pillar's results can easily access the results from the website. Below is some information on the attendees:

- 116 total Attendees (63 on-site, 53 online) + 196 post-event views
 - Researcher/Research & Academia: 58.6%
 - Research Infrastructure: 18.9%
 - Service provider: 7.7%
 - Private sector: 6.9%
 - Policy actor or funder: 6%
 - Standards Organisations: 1.7%

Below is a sample of organisations present at the event that are not part of the consortium, showing that the interest for EOSC-Pillar results extends beyond the consortium:

- | | | |
|--|--|---|
| 1. Ecambi BV | 20. CSUC | 39. Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information (SCSTI) |
| 2. University of Copenhagen | 21. University of West Bohemia | 40. PRACE |
| 3. ALDE/LibDem/External | 22. Kaunas University of Technology | 41. Metapolis |
| 4. Ukrainian National Grid | 23. CSIC | 42. Université de Lorraine |
| 5. Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne | 24. European Commission | 43. Marine Institute |
| 6. IFLA | 25. WWU Münster | 44. The Cyprus Institute |
| 7. KNVI | 26. ECMWF | 45. NI4OS-Europe |
| 8. ISKO-UK | 27. Chouaib Doukkali University | 46. MESR |
| 9. Leibniz Association | 28. German Aerospace Center | 47. Elsevier |
| 10. Hasselt University | 29. Università del Salento | 48. uninett sigma2 |
| 11. open science for open societies – os4os | 30. Ministry of Education and Research | 49. Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) |
| 12. KU Leuven | 31. ESTG/IPP | 50. Ukrainian National Grid, BITP |
| 13. ITM | 32. CERENA/IST | 51. TI Sparkle |
| 14. EurOPDX Research Infrastructure | 33. SUB Göttingen | 52. University of Montpellier |
| 15. University of Milan 'la Statale' | 34. SZTAKI | 53. National Laboratory for Civil Engineering - LNEC |
| 16. University of Bologna | 35. CSC | |
| 17. Stockholm University | 36. Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore | |
| 18. Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore di Milano | 37. fdm.nrw | |
| 19. GWDG | 38. GSI | |

EOSC-Pillar's presence in a vast number of events generated significant visibility for the project and for EOSC across many new communities not represented within the consortium. Several events were even highly localised and held in the host countries' languages.

EOSC-Pillar, through its presence at various groups either formally as a project or informally through members of EOSC-Pillar on a personal capacity, also ensured its input and support to the EOSC governance at various levels as well as to bodies where efforts across projects are harmonised.

The first workshop allowed EOSC-Pillar to gather feedback on some of the proposed EOSC-readiness indicators which eventually contributed to its realisation. The second workshop allowed EOSC-Pillar to advance the discussion on how to incorporate national catalogues (with potentially hundreds of providers and services) into the EOSC Marketplace at a time when onboarding was mostly on an individual provider basis. The final workshop allowed the regional projects to compare their findings in open science, funding, and access policies, providing convergence on years of policy mapping and harmonisation work across the regional projects.

The final event allowed the project to present its significant results not only to the existing consortium and its immediate community but also to the wider audience even beyond the EOSC-Pillar countries that are part of its scope.

2.4 Horizontal Activities KPIs

2.4.1 Communication and Dissemination KPIs and their Contributions to Project KPIs

The KPIs achieved by the project and reported in this report have had direct implications on several Project KPIs as listed in the Grant Agreement.

The table below shows the KPIs and Milestones set to be reached by the end of the project (M42, as per the project extension) which were also outlined in D2.2 [D2.2].

More specifically three Milestones were achieved since the latest deliverable D2.5. These are

- MS6: Organisation and roll-out of second and third workshop:
 - Workshop 2: [Incorporating National and Thematic Service and Resource Catalogues into the EOSC](#)
 - Workshop 3: [Workshop on National Policies relevant to EOSC deployment](#)
- MS8: Organisation and rollout of 10 webinars:
 - [EOSC-Pillar Coordination](#)
 - [National Initiatives - Ger Infoessionion](#)
 - [National Initiatives - Ita Infoessionion](#)
 - [National Initiatives - Fra Infoessionion](#)
 - [National Initiatives Survey results](#)
 - [Synergies between Horizon and European structural and investment funds in EOSC Partnership](#)
 - [Open Science e COVID-19 \(series of 4\)](#)
 - [The role of policies for a sustainable EOSC](#)
 - [EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue](#)
 - [EOSC-Pillar Business Model Workshop](#)
 - [Germany and EOSC for researchers](#)
- MS9: [Final result-oriented event](#)

Element	KPI Target	Results by M42 / Dec-22
Original KPIs from the Description of Work		
Engaged stakeholders in a targeted database	at least 2K	3,129 contacts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End Users: 161 (5%) • Implementers: 2,936 (94%) • Other: 34 (1%) Breakdown by country: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From Austria: 165 (5.3%) • From Belgium: 162 (5.2%) • From France: 356 (11.4%) • From Germany : 1372 (43.8%) • From Italy: 676 (21.6%) Contacts generated from the covered countries vs. the overall database: 2,731 out of 3,129 total contacts (87.3%)

Number of 3rd party events where EOSC-Pillar is visible	Visibility at 80+ 3rd-party events	68 public third party events + 20 meeting series (of 80)
Organisation of webinars and workshops Support to ensure organisation of 14 EOSC-Pillar driven events	450-1,350 people engaged	489 people
EOSC-Pillar results-oriented news pieces	18 Bi-Monthly insights	News pieces: 65 news pieces published
Organisation and roll-out of the three workshops	3 workshops	3
Organisation and roll-out of the ten webinars	10 webinars	14
Final results-oriented event	1 final event	1
Additional KPIs		
Website visits	Moving benchmark tracked monthly	15,760 visits (45,434 page views, 7,602 unique users)
Twitter Followers		1,260 followers
LinkedIn Followers		569 followers
Newsletter	Moving benchmark tracking open rate	2019: 38.50% average open rate 2020: 44.81% average open rate 2021: 33.23% average open rate 2022: 45.13% average open rate
Videos	At least 500 views	1973 views
Webinars	Minimum 70% Attendance Rate	71% (of 70%)

3 Conclusions

This deliverable is an update to D2.2 EOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan [D2.2] and D2.5 EOSC-Pillar Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report [D2.5]. Since the methodology, objectives, stakeholders, campaigns, activities and KPIs largely remain the same, only the final updates and results are noted in this deliverable.

Section 1.2 Stakeholders Analysis and Targeted Messaging reflects how the project continued to keep track of how the fast-changing landscape develops and how the project continued to engage the right stakeholders.

Section 2 EOSC-Pillar Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Report then showed how the activities have been methodically planned carried out along with final results which demonstrate how the communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities have contributed to the project in reaching its goals.

Results of KPIs to-date, both on campaigns and horizontal activities, are also reported. Overall, KPIs have mostly achieved.

Overall, we conclude that our multi-channel strategy for carrying out our communication, dissemination and engagement activities in a structured manner has been successful and supported the project in achieving its goals. While in general, communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement normally plays a supporting role to ensure relevant visibility for the project's results, WP2's activities also yielded a key exploitable result of the project, the Ambassador's Programme, which has now been mapped as relevant by the EOSC Association to the work of the EOSC Advisory Group Task Force on Researcher Engagement and Adoption.